

LINGUISTIC AND REGIONAL STUDIES IN RUSSIAN
AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract. The educational principle of active communication, which is one of the leading principles in teaching Russian to foreigners, is impossible without the linguistic and cultural aspect of teaching. Linguistic and regional studies is a direction, on the one hand, which includes language teaching, and on the other, providing certain information about the country through the language being studied. Language is one of the main characteristics of a nation and is rooted in the history, culture, religion and life of the native people. The goal of linguistic and regional studies is to ensure communicative competence in acts of intercultural communication.

Keywords: Linguistics, language, competence, method, learning.

INTRODUCTION

In the process of learning Russian, a foreign student learns to speak, read, write, i.e. learns to understand, reproduce and produce Russian speech. The linguistic (linguistic) level of language learning is an important condition for the student's communicative competence. But the practice of teaching RFL has proven the impossibility of "adequate communication in the target language if this language is studied only as a new code, in isolation from the national culture it expresses" [2]. Thus, it is obvious that the cultural and historical awareness of a foreigner is a necessary condition for adequate language proficiency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

V. G. Kostomarov and E. M. Vereshchagin, defining linguistic and regional studies as “a set of techniques and methods of presentation, consolidation and activation of information from national culture in the language educational process,” [1] thereby emphasized the importance of introducing a linguistic and cultural aspect into teaching methods Russian as a foreign language.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Coming to another country, a student needs to get to know the place where he lives and studies better. Such acquaintance should occur not only through the information that he receives in Russian language lessons. In this situation, the extracurricular work of the teacher and student also plays an important role. No one doubts how advisable and important it is to hold additional conversations, lectures that include local history information, organize competitions, evenings, and also conduct special educational excursions. An important factor in mastering educational material is interest and motivation.

Linguistic and regional studies stimulate the activation of students' speech and mental activity, contribute to the enrichment of vocabulary, and expand the scope of speech situations. The linguistic and cultural aspect of teaching the Russian language can be qualified as inter-level, which permeates all system levels of teaching the Russian language. Regional studies material contributes to the development of communication skills in various areas of communication. Mastering a variety of information about our country helps to adequately perceive the surrounding reality. Therefore, teaching Russian as a foreign language involves a regional studies aspect, which is carried out as a process of developing students' regional studies competence.

The most important source of historical and cultural information about the region and the city for a foreign student is an educational text adapted to the level of his preparation. Therefore, the basis for a local history reading aid should be work with the text, which provides for both compliance with traditional general methodological and general didactic principles of teaching reading, and

compliance with the specific requirements of the linguistic and regional aspect of teaching the Russian language, in particular:

- a) consistency in the presentation of linguistic and cultural information;
- b) the ratio of current background knowledge and background knowledge of cultural heritage from the point of view of communicative value;
- c) presentation of regional studies material in a text system;
- d) correlation of linguocultural visual clarity with the content of linguocultural educational texts [3].

Work on a text containing local history material is complex: the text presents meaningful information, promotes the development of speech and reading skills, as well as mastery of reading in Russian. Thus, the study of culture occurs in the forms of the language being studied.

The goals of teaching linguistics and regional studies are:

- 1) improvement of speech skills in the socio-cultural sphere of communication;
- 2) formation of skills in reasoned monologue statements;
- 3) developing the skills to participate in discussions of general scientific, socio-political and social-problematic content;
- 4) developing the skills to understand the main meaning and details of the content of the original text of a general scientific, social-problematic, socio-political nature in the process of reading and listening;
- 5) developing skills in annotating, summarizing and translating texts of general scientific content;
- 6) mastery of new vocabulary and word-formation models characteristic of book speech;
- 7) improving writing skills.

Depending on the tasks at a particular stage of training, certain requirements must be imposed on a regional studies text as educational material, namely:

- a) the educational text must be relevant, arouse interest among students, and contain the necessary information of a cognitive, regional and educational nature;
- b) the content and information potential of the text must correspond to a certain type of reading;
- c) the structure of the text must correspond to the planned types of work;
- d) the language of the educational text is minimized and compressed depending on the goals, objectives and stages of training;
- e) the volume of the educational text is regulated by the educational time allocated for its reading and the amount of regional information presented in it;
- f) the educational text on regional studies topics must be consistent with the entire system of texts in the textbook (the principle of concentricity in the presentation of regional studies information is maintained) and have its own clearly defined goals.

CONCLUSION

Thus, regional studies competence, along with linguistic competence, creates the basis for the formation and development of communicative competence of foreign students. The acquired knowledge contributes to normative speech behavior in communication situations, the adequacy of the perception of what is heard, read and written.

REFERENCES

1. Vereshchagin E. M., Kostomarov V. G. Language and culture. Linguistic and regional studies in teaching Russian as a foreign language. - M., 2013.
2. Shcherbacheva N.I. The place and role of linguistic and regional studies in the study of oriental languages: materials of a scientific conference. - M., 2013.
3. Turchaninova E. M. On the question of the typology of linguistic and cultural educational texts at the initial stage of teaching the Russian language: collection. scientific and methodological articles "Linguistic and regional studies in teaching Russian as a foreign language." - M.: "Russian language", 2019.

4. Rodenko A. V., Konek O. P., Tubol N. A., Burnos E. Yu. Guidelines on the aspect of “Linguistics” for 1st year foreign students. - Sumy: SumSU Publishing House, 2015.